

Perceptions of Tech-Voc Instructors and Students on The Beneficiality of Translanguaging in Technical-Vocational Classroom Instruction

Jerylvin A. Rabago

Instructor I, Mariano Marcos State University, Laoag City

ABSTRACT: This study determined the perceptions of Technical-Vocational (Tech-Voc) instructors and students regarding the beneficiality of translanguaging in classroom instruction across the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains. A sequential explanatory mixed-methods design was employed, consisting of a descriptive survey followed by focus group discussions (FGDs) to validate and explain the quantitative findings. The participants included 50 Tech-Voc instructors and 1,156 students enrolled in the Bachelor in Automotive Technology and Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology programs. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequency counts, while qualitative data were examined through thematic analysis. Results revealed that instructors overwhelmingly perceived translanguaging as highly beneficial, with 100% strongly agreeing that it enhances students' reasoning skills, decision-making, active participation in practical activities, enjoyment of learning, and attentiveness during class discussions. Similarly, students reported highly positive perceptions, particularly in learning independently ($f = 1,138$), comprehending concepts and facts ($f = 1,121$), reflecting on their learning ($f = 1,106$), measuring and weighing materials accurately ($f = 1,039$), and finding learning natural and interesting ($f = 1,071$). Qualitative findings generated five themes: enhanced comprehension of technical concepts, improved critical thinking and problem-solving skills, greater participation and performance in practical tasks, increased confidence and classroom engagement, and affirmation of linguistic and cultural identity. The study concludes that translanguaging is an effective pedagogical strategy that supports holistic learner development and promotes a more inclusive, engaging, and meaningful learning environment in Tech-Voc classrooms.

Corresponding Author:

Jerylvin A. Rabago

Published Online:

June 24, 2026

License:

This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

KEYWORDS:

classroom engagement, learner development, multilingual instruction, technical-vocational education, translanguaging

Cite the Article: Rabago, J.A.(2026). *Perceptions of Tech-Voc Instructors and Students on The Beneficiality of Translanguaging in Technical-Vocational Classroom Instruction. International Journal of Human Research and Social Science Studies,3(6),638-646.* <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijhrsss/14-2026-Vol03I06>

INTRODUCTION

English has long served as the primary medium of instruction in Philippine higher education institutions (HEIs) as part of the country's response to globalization and the growing demand for a globally competitive workforce. The widespread use of English in tertiary education reflects its role as the country's second language and an essential communication tool in academic and professional settings. Consequently, universities continue to strengthen English proficiency among students and faculty through institutional language policies that encourage the consistent use of English in classroom instruction.

In technical-vocational (Tech-Voc) education, however, the exclusive use of English presents unique instructional challenges. Unlike other academic disciplines, Tech-Voc instruction emphasizes practical demonstrations, procedural learning, and the mastery of technical concepts that are often more effectively explained using learners' familiar languages. Dixon and Peake (2008) observed that the rigid use of English in technical instruction frequently creates communication barriers, particularly when technical concepts lack direct lexical equivalents in English or when contextual explanations are necessary. Similarly, Purwati et al. (2023) found that both Tech-Voc instructors and students experienced developmental challenges in English proficiency, making it

difficult to articulate technical ideas effectively. Their findings attributed these difficulties to the nature of technical-vocational education, which prioritizes mechanical and technological competencies over linguistic competence. Bravo-Sotelo (2020) likewise noted that instructors naturally shift between languages during demonstrations and practical applications to facilitate immediate understanding of technical concepts.

This instructional practice is consistent with the concept of translanguaging, which MacSwan (2022) described as the dynamic use of multiple linguistic resources to maximize communication and understanding. Rather than viewing languages as separate systems, translanguaging enables teachers and learners to draw upon their entire linguistic repertoire to construct meaning, clarify concepts, and facilitate learning. Within Tech-Voc education, where procedural accuracy and conceptual understanding are essential, translanguaging provides opportunities for instructors to contextualize complex technical ideas while allowing students to actively participate without being constrained by limited English proficiency.

Despite its pedagogical value, many higher education institutions continue to uphold English-dominant language policies. In the college where this study was conducted, instructors and students encounter difficulties in explaining and understanding technical concepts presented in English-language textbooks, manuals, and online resources. These challenges became more pronounced following the university's declaration as an English-speaking institution and the subsequent approval of its Language Policy by the Board of Regents, which promotes English as the primary medium of instruction and official communication. While this policy seeks to enhance English proficiency in response to reports of declining English competence among Filipino learners, it also creates tensions between institutional expectations and actual classroom practices.

From a sociolinguistic perspective, such language policies represent forms of language dominance that may limit students' opportunities to express themselves using languages with which they are more familiar. Fillmore and Snow (2018) argued that educators should recognize and respect students' home languages as valuable instructional resources rather than viewing them as barriers to learning. Bernardo (2022) similarly demonstrated that although American English remains the preferred standard in English language assessment, Philippine English and other local language varieties naturally emerge in instructional contexts. These findings suggest that multilingual classroom interactions are an inevitable feature of Philippine education and should be viewed as educational resources rather than instructional deficiencies.

Canagarajah (2011) further emphasized that competent users of English in multilingual societies should be capable of moving flexibly between English and their local languages while recognizing the legitimacy of different language varieties. This linguistic flexibility is fostered through translanguaging, enabling learners to negotiate meaning across languages according to the communicative demands of the classroom. Nevertheless, the adoption of translanguaging remains influenced by institutional structures and language ideologies. Tupas (2014) argued that these challenges are rooted in historical, social, and institutional conditions that continue to privilege English over local languages, particularly as higher education institutions pursue internationalization initiatives.

The persistence of English-only policies has also generated concerns regarding equity and inclusion. Although such policies assume that increased exposure to English accelerates language acquisition, empirical evidence suggests otherwise. Kani and Igsen (2022) reported that English-only policies often create experiences of discrimination and frustration among learners who are less proficient in English. Likewise, Dobinson et al. (2023) found that many teachers acknowledged the positive role of students' first languages in supporting learning despite institutional language restrictions. These studies indicate that strategic use of translanguaging can enhance classroom communication without diminishing the importance of English as an academic language.

Within Philippine higher education, educators likewise recognize the practical value of translanguaging. Tarrayo et al. (2019) reported that while instructors continue to regard English as the standard language for academic instruction, they also acknowledged the necessity of utilizing students' local languages to facilitate comprehension, particularly in linguistically diverse classrooms. Cummins (2019) explained that translanguaging enables learners to build upon their prior linguistic knowledge, thereby promoting deeper conceptual understanding and supporting the transfer of learning to more complex contexts. Through this process, students are able to strengthen not only their language proficiency but also their academic performance and confidence.

Despite the growing body of literature supporting translanguaging, limited research has specifically examined its perceived beneficiality within technical-vocational education in Philippine higher education. Existing studies have largely focused on language policies, English proficiency, and multilingual classroom practices, with little attention given to how Tech-Voc instructors and students perceive the benefits of translanguaging in facilitating learning. Understanding these perceptions is particularly important because Tech-Voc instruction requires the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical skill development in multilingual classroom settings.

In response to this research gap, the present study examined the perceptions of Tech-Voc instructors and students regarding the beneficiality of translanguaging in technical-vocational classroom instruction. Specifically, the study focused on its perceived contributions to the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains of learning. By examining these dimensions, the study aims to provide empirical evidence that may guide language practices in technical-vocational instruction and contribute to the development of more inclusive and pedagogically responsive classroom environments.

Objectives of the Study

The study generally aimed to determine the perceptions of Tech-Voc instructors and students on the beneficiality of translanguaging in technical-vocational classroom instruction.

Specifically, it sought to:

- determine the perceptions of Tech-Voc instructors on the beneficiality of translanguaging in terms of cognitive, psychomotor, and affective dimensions in classroom instruction.
- determine the perceptions of Tech-Voc students on the beneficiality of translanguaging in terms of cognitive, psychomotor, and affective dimensions in classroom instruction.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design, wherein quantitative data were collected and analyzed first, followed by qualitative data to explain and validate the quantitative findings. The quantitative phase utilized a descriptive survey to determine the perceptions of Tech-Voc instructors and students regarding the beneficiality of translanguaging in terms of cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains. The qualitative phase, through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), provided supporting explanations and deeper insights into the survey results.

Purposive sampling was employed to select the study participants. The respondents consisted of all 50 Tech-Voc instructors teaching in the Bachelor in Automotive Technology (BAT) and Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology (BSIT) programs, as well as 1,356 first- to third-year Tech-Voc students enrolled in these programs. Fourth-year students were excluded because they were undergoing on-the-job training and had no regular classroom instruction during the data collection period. Participation was voluntary, and only respondents who provided informed consent were included. For the qualitative phase, two FGDs were conducted with a total of 20 participants, comprising 10 instructors and 10 students representing the different degree programs.

Ethical clearance was obtained from an institution, followed by approval from the college administration before data collection commenced. After explaining the purpose of the study and obtaining informed consent, questionnaires were administered to the selected instructor and student respondents at their most convenient time. Upon completion of the survey, two FGDs were conducted to validate and enrich the quantitative findings. The discussions were guided by an interview protocol, audio-recorded with participants' consent, and conducted in a secure and comfortable venue. Participants' identities were protected through coding, and confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the research process.

Survey data were analyzed using frequency count to describe the perceptions of Tech-Voc instructors and students regarding the beneficiality of translanguaging across the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains. The qualitative data obtained from the FGDs were analyzed through thematic analysis following the six-step framework of Braun and Clarke (2006): familiarization with the data, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing the report. The qualitative findings were used to corroborate and provide deeper explanations for the quantitative results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and interprets the findings on the perceived beneficiality of translanguaging in technical-vocational (tech-voc) classroom instruction. The results are organized according to three domains of learning—cognitive, psychomotor, and affective benefits—as perceived by both Tech-Voc instructors and students. Quantitative findings from the survey are further supported by qualitative data from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), providing a comprehensive explanation of how translanguaging functions within tech-voc education.

A. Perceptions of Tech-Voc Instructors on the Beneficiality of Translanguaging in Classroom Instruction

Table 1 presents the perceptions of Tech-Voc instructors regarding the beneficiality of translanguaging in classroom instruction across the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains. The findings provide insights into how instructors view translanguaging as a pedagogical strategy that supports students' learning, skill development, and classroom engagement.

Table 1. Perceptions of Tech-Voc Instructors on the Beneficiality of Translanguaging

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
A. Cognitive Benefits				
<i>Translanguaging is beneficial in:</i>	4	3	2	1
	<i>(f)</i>	<i>(f)</i>	<i>(f)</i>	<i>(f)</i>
1. comprehending concepts and facts.	45	5	0	0
2. understanding technical terms and concepts.	43	7	0	0
3. exercising reasoning skills during classroom instructions.	50	0	0	0
4. thinking logically during classroom discussions.	44	6	0	0
5. making choices based on reasoned arguments.	50	0	0	0

6. learning on their own.	44	6	0	0
7. reflecting with their own learning.	46	4	0	0
8. solving problems using the required technical skills and knowledge.	49	1	0	0
9. developing the ability to apply what they have learned in the classroom.	45	5	0	0
10. adjusting their thinking skills to learn the lesson.	44	6	0	0

B. Psychomotor Benefits*Translanguaging is beneficial in:*

1. assembling machines and equipment efficiently.	49	1	0	0
2. performing actively during skills demonstration and practical applications.	50	0	0	0
3. manipulating learning materials and other tech-voc equipment.	44	6	0	0
4. measuring and weighing the needed materials for classroom performance.	50	0	0	0
5. demonstrating appropriate health and safety practices.	45	5	0	0
6. constructing projects or outputs creatively.	47	3	0	0
7. executing the appropriate use of tools and facilities.	46	4	0	0
8. arranging and following procedural steps in coming up with the desired tech-voc outputs or projects.	49	1	0	0
9. reconstructing outputs based on the changing context and parameters of technology education.	50	0	0	0
10. designing products based on the designated course outcomes.	44	6	0	0

C. Affective Benefits*Translanguaging is beneficial in:*

1. making students comfortable and confident in talking.	45	5	0	0
2. making learning as informal, natural and interesting.	43	7	0	0
3. making learning enjoyable and fun.	50	0	0	0
4. making students more attentive during class discussions.	50	0	0	0
5. expressing their ideas, opinions and feeling more freely.	44	6	0	0
6. feeling the sense of belongingness with each other and within the class.	46	4	0	0
7. showing high motivation to go to school.	49	1	0	0
8. understanding more the feelings, needs, and interests of their classmates.	47	3	0	0
9. cultivating greater love and appreciation to their native language.	48	2	0	0
10. expressing what they feel with no fear of language barriers.	49	1	0	0

Cognitive Dimension

The results revealed that Tech-Voc instructors perceived translanguaging as highly beneficial in enhancing students' cognitive development. All instructor-respondents (100%) strongly agreed that translanguaging helps students exercise reasoning skills during classroom instruction (Indicator 3) and make choices based on reasoned arguments (Indicator 5). Likewise, 98% strongly agreed that it supports problem-solving using technical skills and knowledge (Indicator 8).

These findings suggest that translanguaging facilitates higher-order thinking processes by allowing students to draw upon their full linguistic repertoire when analyzing concepts, making decisions, and solving technical problems. Lin & Leung (2023) emphasized that translanguaging enables learners to generate, process, and communicate ideas more effectively because they are not constrained by a single language. Similarly, Wildeman et al. (2022) noted that translanguaging functions as a cognitive resource that supports learners in addressing complex academic and technical tasks.

In the context of technical-vocational education, the use of students' familiar languages allows them to comprehend technical concepts more deeply, articulate logical explanations, and formulate practical solutions to workplace-related problems. Consequently, translanguaging promotes meaningful learning and strengthens students' ability to transfer classroom knowledge to authentic situations.

Psychomotor Dimension

The instructors likewise perceived translanguaging as highly beneficial in developing students' psychomotor competencies. All respondents strongly agreed that translanguaging enhances students' active participation during skills demonstrations and practical applications (Indicator 2), assists them in measuring and weighing materials accurately (Indicator 4), and supports them in reconstructing outputs based on changing technological contexts (Indicator 9).

These findings affirm that language plays a crucial role in facilitating procedural understanding and task performance. According to Kurtz et al. (2017), translanguaging creates opportunities for learners to express procedures and technical processes through languages they understand best, thereby increasing confidence and participation during practical activities. Likewise, Dahalan et al. (2023) argued that translanguaging strengthens students' technical competencies by helping them understand instructions and adapt their outputs to evolving technological requirements.

The findings imply that students perform technical tasks more effectively when they can discuss procedures, clarify instructions, and collaborate with peers using familiar linguistic resources. Such opportunities reduce communication barriers and improve performance in laboratory activities and skills-based learning experiences.

Affective Dimension

The instructors also strongly perceived translanguaging as beneficial in fostering positive affective outcomes among students. All respondents strongly agreed that translanguaging makes learning enjoyable and fun (Indicator 3) and helps students become more attentive during classroom discussions (Indicator 4). Furthermore, 98% strongly agreed that translanguaging promotes high motivation to attend school (Indicator 7) and enables students to express themselves without fear of language barriers (Indicator 10).

These findings support Miller's (2020) assertion that translanguaging promotes a supportive and non-threatening learning environment. When students are allowed to use their home language alongside English, they experience greater comfort and confidence in classroom interactions. As a result, they become more engaged, motivated, and willing to participate in learning activities.

The findings further suggest that translanguaging validates students' linguistic identities and fosters a sense of belonging in the classroom. By recognizing multiple languages as valuable resources for learning, teachers create inclusive environments where students feel respected and empowered to contribute.

The survey findings were substantiated by the instructors' interview responses. Several instructors emphasized that students are better able to present logical arguments and explain technical concepts when allowed to use their mother tongue. Others observed that translanguaging increases students' participation in practical activities and improves collaboration during project development. Moreover, instructors described translanguaging as a localized and natural teaching approach that sustains students' attention and interest in learning. These observations align with the principles of multimodal learning, which recognizes language as one of several resources through which meaning is constructed and communicated (Jewitt, 2014; Morell, 2018; Munirah et al., 2021; Van Leeuwen, 2014). Thus, translanguaging serves as an important pedagogical strategy for supporting students' cognitive, psychomotor, and affective development in Tech-Voc education. The following statements from the instructor respondents support the findings presented in Table 1.

“Our students can express their ideas logically when they use the Iloko language. I find it also to be useful whenever I ask them to debate on something especially if the topic requires a very technical answer. It makes their reasons sound more logical and acceptable.” - Instructor 1, on cognitive benefits

“They can do more and actively participate in my class because their native tongue is strategically used. Whenever they do their activities, they would opt to use the Iloko language to maximize their performance.” - Instructor 3, on psychomotor benefits

“I really find it beneficial because my method of teaching feels to be more localized and natural which is really helpful on the part of the students.” - Instructor 5, on affective benefits

B. Perceptions of Tech-Voc Students on the Beneficiality of Translanguaging in Classroom Instruction

Table 2 shows the perceptions of Tech-Voc students on the beneficiality of translanguaging in classroom instruction. Specifically, it presents the students' views on how translanguaging contributes to their cognitive development, psychomotor performance, and affective experiences during learning activities.

Table 2. Perceptions of Tech-Voc Students on the Beneficiality of Translanguaging

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
A. Cognitive Benefits				
<i>Translanguaging is beneficial in:</i>	4	3	2	1
	<i>(f)</i>	<i>(f)</i>	<i>(f)</i>	<i>(f)</i>
1. comprehending concepts and facts.	1121	35	0	0
2. understanding technical terms and concepts.	1053	103	0	0
3. exercising reasoning skills during classroom instructions.	1101	55	0	0
4. thinking logically during classroom discussions.	997	159	0	0
5. making choices based on reasoned arguments.	965	191	0	0
6. learning on their own.	1138	18	0	0
7. reflecting with their own learning.	1106	50	0	0
8. solving problems using the required technical skills and knowledge.	967	189	0	0
9. developing the ability to apply what they have learned in the classroom.	1088	68	0	0
10. adjusting their thinking skills to learn the lesson.	1088	68	0	0
B. Psychomotor Benefits				
<i>Translanguaging is beneficial in:</i>				
1. assembling machines and equipment efficiently.	945	211	0	0
2. performing actively during skills demonstration and practical applications.	1024	132	0	0
3. manipulating learning materials and other tech-voc equipment.	1014	142	0	0
4. measuring and weighing the needed materials for classroom performance.	1039	117	0	0
5. demonstrating appropriate health and safety practices.	793	363	0	0
6. constructing projects or outputs creatively.	911	245	0	0
7. executing the appropriate use of tools and facilities.	724	432	0	0
8. arranging and following procedural steps in coming up with the desired tech-voc outputs or projects.	1001	155	0	0
9. reconstructing outputs based on the required objectives of technology education.	1029	127	0	0
10. designing products based on the designated course outcomes.	953	203	0	0
C. Affective Benefits				
<i>Translanguaging is beneficial in:</i>				
1. being comfortable and confident in talking.	910	246	0	0
2. finding learning as informal, natural and interesting.	1071	85	0	0
3. feeling that learning is enjoyable and fun.	1033	123	0	0
4. being more attentive during class discussions.	1045	111	0	0
5. expressing ideas, opinions and feelings more freely.	996	160	0	0
6. feeling the sense of belongingness with classmates and within the class.	943	213	0	0
7. showing high motivation to go to school.	940	216	0	0
8. understanding more the feelings, needs, and interests of their classmates.	977	179	0	0
9. cultivating greater love and appreciation to their native language.	1057	99	0	0
10. expressing what they feel with no fear of language barriers.	985	171	0	0

Cognitive Dimension

The findings indicate that students overwhelmingly perceived translanguaging as beneficial to their cognitive development. The highest-rated indicators were learning independently (Indicator 6; $f = 1,138$), comprehending concepts and facts (Indicator 1; $f = 1,121$), and reflecting on their own learning (Indicator 7; $f = 1,106$).

These results suggest that translanguaging supports self-regulated learning by allowing students to access, process, and evaluate information through languages they understand best. Velasco and García (2014) found that translanguaging helps learners scaffold their understanding and overcome learning difficulties by strategically utilizing their linguistic resources. Similarly, Carstens (2016) reported that translanguaging enhances conceptual understanding, facilitates meaning-making, and promotes reflective learning among bilingual students.

For Tech-Voc learners, the opportunity to use familiar languages appears to facilitate comprehension of technical concepts and encourages independent learning, thereby strengthening their cognitive engagement with instructional content.

Psychomotor Dimension

Students likewise recognized the psychomotor benefits of translanguaging. The highest-rated indicators were measuring and weighing materials needed for classroom performance (Indicator 4; $f = 1,039$), reconstructing outputs based on instructional objectives (Indicator 9; $f = 1,029$), and actively participating in skills demonstrations and practical applications (Indicator 2; $f = 1,024$).

These findings support Lin & Leung (2023) assertion that translanguaging helps students overcome communication barriers that may hinder performance during classroom activities. By understanding instructions more clearly and communicating effectively with peers and instructors, learners become more capable of performing technical tasks accurately and confidently.

The findings are also consistent with Rivera and Mazak's (2017) study, which found that translanguaging enhances student performance by facilitating comprehension of complex concepts and promoting meaningful teacher-student interactions. In Tech-Voc classrooms, clearer communication appears to contribute directly to successful execution of hands-on activities and technical procedures.

Affective Dimension

Students also reported strong affective benefits associated with translanguaging. The highest-rated indicators were finding learning informal, natural, and interesting (Indicator 2; $f = 1,071$), developing greater love and appreciation for their native language (Indicator 9; $f = 1,057$), and becoming more attentive during class discussions (Indicator 4; $f = 1,045$).

These findings support Bravo-Sotelo (2020) view that translanguaging creates more authentic and meaningful learning experiences by reducing linguistic barriers between teachers and students. Through translanguaging, classroom interactions become more natural, accessible, and learner-centered. Furthermore, Cummins (2019) emphasized that the use of students' home languages strengthens cultural identity while supporting academic achievement.

The results indicate that translanguaging not only enhances engagement but also nurtures positive attitudes toward learning and language diversity. Students become more attentive, comfortable, and motivated when their linguistic backgrounds are recognized and valued within the classroom.

The interview responses reinforced the survey findings. Students shared that they understood lessons more clearly, remembered concepts better, and worked more independently when teachers incorporated their native language into instruction. Others noted that using their mother tongue during laboratory activities enabled them to perform tasks more efficiently and explain technical procedures more accurately.

Students also reported increased confidence during recitations and classroom discussions because they did not fear being judged for their English proficiency. These observations support Yildiz and Celik's (2020) claim that translanguaging maximizes learners' cognitive, psychomotor, communicative, and affective development. Likewise, Velasco and García (2014) argued that translanguaging enhances critical thinking, creativity, and active participation, all of which are essential competencies in technical-vocational education. The following statements from the instructor respondents support the findings presented in Table 2.

Mas makaubraak a maymaysa, sir no adda ilokano na bassit tay instructions ni mestromi. Mas matandanaanak a nasayaat. (I can work independently, sir whenever my teacher used the Iloko language and I can also remember the topics we have discussed.) - Student 1, on cognitive benefits

Mas maawatak tay topicsmi, sir no iyilokanon mestromi tay discussionsna. (I can understand the topic well, sir if our teacher uses the Iloko language discussing concepts and facts.) - Student 2, on cognitive benefits

Sa totoo lang, sir makaperformkami a nasayaat no agsasaritakami nga Ilokano usarmi during laboratory activitiesmi. (To be honest, sir we can perform efficiently if we use the Iloko language when we communicate with each other during laboratory activities.) - Student 3, on psychomotor benefits

Haanko ammo nga iexplain tay panangmeasuremi kadagiti materials and ingredientsmi iso agilokanoak nukwa. (I do not know how to explain the proper way of measuring our materials and ingredients that is why I would use the Iloko language.) - Student 4, on psychomotor benefits

Mas kaykayaiko no agilokano ni mestrami, sir kasi makarecite nak nukwa a nasayaat. Diak mabuteng kasi makitak nga haan suna agpabain no madikami makaenglish. (I like it better when my teacher uses the Iloko language because I get to recite during classroom recitations. I am not afraid to speak because my teacher does not humiliate us if we cannot express ourselves in English.) - Student 5, on affective benefits

Nagkomportable feelingna, sir no allowed kami agusar Ilokano no madama klasemi. (I feel comfortable if we are allowed to use the Iloko language during class discussions) - Student 6, on affective benefits

Overall, both the survey and interview data indicate that students perceive translanguaging as a valuable instructional strategy that promotes understanding, participation, and engagement in Tech-Voc classrooms.

CONCLUSION

This study found that both Tech-Voc instructors and students perceived translanguaging as highly beneficial in classroom instruction across the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains. The findings revealed that translanguaging enhances students' understanding of technical concepts, reasoning abilities, independent learning, and problem-solving skills. Likewise, it supports the development of psychomotor competencies by improving students' participation in practical activities, skills demonstrations, and the execution of technical tasks. These findings suggest that the strategic use of learners' linguistic resources contributes to more effective learning and performance in technical-vocational education.

Furthermore, translanguaging was perceived to foster positive affective outcomes by increasing students' confidence, motivation, attentiveness, and willingness to participate in classroom discussions. The qualitative findings reinforced these results, highlighting five key themes: enhanced comprehension of technical concepts, improved critical thinking and problem-solving skills, greater participation in practical tasks, increased confidence and classroom engagement, and affirmation of linguistic and cultural identity. Overall, the study concludes that translanguaging is a valuable and effective pedagogical approach that promotes holistic learner development and creates a more inclusive and meaningful learning environment in Tech-Voc classrooms.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that Tech-Voc instructors strategically integrate translanguaging into classroom instruction to enhance students' cognitive, psychomotor, and affective development. Schools and educational leaders may provide professional development programs that equip teachers with effective translanguaging practices and multilingual teaching strategies. Curriculum developers may also consider incorporating translanguaging-friendly learning activities and instructional materials that recognize learners' linguistic resources as assets in learning. Furthermore, future researchers may conduct similar studies in different educational contexts and disciplines to further validate the beneficiality of translanguaging and explore its long-term impact on students' academic achievement, skills development, and classroom engagement.

Declaration of AI Used

The author declare that artificial intelligence (AI) technology was utilized during the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, ChatGPT (OpenAI) was used to assist in reviewing, refining, and enhancing the language, coherence, organization, and clarity of the manuscript. The AI tool was also employed to verify statistical computations and improve the presentation of results. However, the AI did not generate, modify, or interpret the research data, findings, or conclusions of the study.

REFERENCES

1. Bernardo, A. S. (2022). Language Teaching: Development, Structure, and Sociology of English in the Philippines. In *Philippine English* (1st ed., pp. 283–296). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429427824-29>
2. Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
3. Bravo-Sotelo, K. P. (2020). Exploring the Tagalog-English Code-Switching types used for mathematics classroom instruction. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.22492/ije.8.1.03>

4. Canagarajah, S. (2011). Translanguaging in the classroom: Emerging issues for research and pedagogy. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 2(2011), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110239331.1>
5. Carstens, A. (2016). Translanguaging as a vehicle for L2 acquisition and L1 development: students' perceptions. *Language Matters*, 47(2), 203–222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10228195.2016.1153135>
6. Cummins, J. (2019). The Emergence of Translanguaging Pedagogy: A Dialogue between Theory and Practice. *Fordham Research Commons*. <https://fordham.bepress.com/jmer/vol9/iss1/13>
7. Dahalan, F., Alias, N., & Shaharom, M. S. N. (2023). Gamification and Game Based Learning for Vocational Education and Training: A Systematic Literature review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(2), 1279–1317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11548-w>
8. Dixon, K., & Peake, K. (2008). "Straight for English": Using school language policy to resist multilingualism. *Repository@Nottingham (University of Nottingham)*, 7(1), 73–90. <https://nottingham-repository.worktribe.com/output/27087237>
9. Dobinson, T., Dryden, S., Dovchin, S., Gong, Q., & Mercieca, P. (2023). Translanguaging and "English only" at universities. *TESOL Quarterly*, 58(1), 307–333. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.3232>
10. Fillmore, L. W., & Snow, C. E. (2018). What teachers need to know about language. In *Channel View Publications eBooks* (pp. 8–51). <https://doi.org/10.2307/jj.22730499.5>
11. Jewitt, C. (2014). The Routledge Handbook of Multimodal Analysis (2nd Edition). In *Routledge eBooks*. <http://eprints.ioe.ac.uk/18336/>
12. Kani, Z. G., & İğsen, H. (2022). Bilingual English teachers' perspectives on "English-only" policies in an EFL setting. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 17(1), 127–141. <https://doi.org/10.29329/epasr.2022.248.7>
13. Kurtz, S., Silverman, J., Draper, J., Van Dalen, J., & Platt, F. W. (2017). *Teaching and learning communication skills in medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315378398>
14. Lin, S. H., & Leung, A. H. (2023). ESL classroom interactions in a translanguaging space. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 15(6), 2397–2425. <https://doi.org/10.1515/applirev-2022-0202>
15. MacSwan, J. (2022). Multilingual Perspectives on Translanguaging. In *Multilingual Matters eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781800415690>
16. Miller, K. (2020). Effectively enabling translanguaging in the classroom. *Digital Commons - Hamline (Hamline University)*. https://digitalcommons.hamline.edu/hse_cp/515
17. Morell, T. (2018). Multimodal competence and effective interactive lecturing. *System*, 77, 70–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2017.12.006>
18. Munirah, M., Thaba, A., & Yusuf, A. B. (2021). Translanguaging in the communicative practice of buyers and sellers in traditional market. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v11i2.36029>
19. Purwati, D., Fathirma'ruf, F., Lakehu, A., & Taufik, T. (2024). Investigating Indonesian EFL preservice teachers' digital technological awareness and their challenges in EFL learning: A case study. *Journal on English as a Foreign Language*, 14(1), 152–178. <https://doi.org/10.23971/jefl.v14i1.7625>
20. Rivera, A. J., & Mazak, C. M. (2017). Analyzing student perceptions on translanguaging: A case study of a Puerto Rican University classroom. *HOW*, 24(1), 122–138. <https://doi.org/10.19183/how.24.1.312>
21. Tarrayo, V. N., Hernandez, P. J. S., & Claustro, J. M. a. S. (2019). Teachers and research practices: Perspectives from English language educators in a Philippine university. *the Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 45(12), 73–90. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.202v45n12.5>
22. Tupas, R. (2014). Inequalities of multilingualism: challenges to mother tongue-based multilingual education. *Language and Education*, 29(2), 112–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2014.977295>
23. Van Leeuwen, T. (2014). Critical discourse analysis and multimodality. *University of Southern Denmark Research Portal (University of Southern Denmark)*, 281–297. <https://portal.findresearcher.sdu.dk/da/publications/d69047b5-f9e9-4b59-bb0a-a80f11546d70>
24. Velasco, P., & García, O. (2014). Translanguaging and the writing of bilingual learners. *Bilingual Research Journal*, 37(1), 6–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15235882.2014.893270>
25. Wildeman, E., Koopman, M., & Beijjaard, D. (2022). Fostering subject teachers' integrated language teaching in technical vocational education: Results of a professional development program. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 112, 103626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103626>
26. Yildiz, Y., & Celik, B. (2020). The use of scaffolding techniques in language learning: Extending the level of understanding. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Educational Studies*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v7i3p148>